

COMPLEX CHROMIUM SELENATES.

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Two modifications of chromium selenate, blue and green, have been described and their properties studied. They differ from the compounds described by Meyer.

Three different modifications of chromium sulphate are described one of which is violet and the other two green. The green chromic sulphates, from a consideration of their properties, are regarded to have complex constitutions. One of these, in which all the sulphate radicals are non-ionisable, is considered to be chromium-chromic sulphate, $\text{Cr}[\text{Cr}(\text{SO}_4)_3]$. Many complex compounds of chromium sulphate, such as chromo-sulphates, chromo-sulpho-chromates and the corresponding acids have been described by Re-coura (*Compt. rend.*, 1892, **114**, 477; 1893, **116**, 1367; 1893, **117**, 37, 101; *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1896, *iii*, **15**, 315; 1897, *iii*, **17**, 934).

In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 653) it has been shown that chromic chromate also possesses a complex constitution, $\text{Cr}^{III}[\text{Cr}^{III}(\text{CrO}_4)_3]_3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{Cr}^{III}[\text{Cr}^{III}(\text{CrO}_4)_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$

It is well known that sulphuric and selenic acids resemble each other closely and it was not unexpected that complex compounds of chromium and selenic acid analogous to complex chromium sulphate would be reported. Meyer (*Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1921, **118**, 1) has described two modifications of complex chromium selenates, green and violet, besides a triselenatochromic acid. Sarkar and Bhattacharyya have studied the properties of chromoselenic acid and chromosulphoselenic acid and their salts (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **7**, 765).

The violet and green selenates of Meyer were represented by the following constitution and formulae respectively. $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]_2(\text{SeO}_4)_3$, 3 or 4 H_2O prepared from violet chromium nitrate and concentrated selenic acid, and $[\text{Cr}(\text{SeO}_4)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5]_2\text{SeO}_4$ or $[\{\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6\}_2\text{SeO}_4](\text{SeO}_4)_2$ prepared from the violet salt by drying it at 90°.

In the present paper two modifications of chromium selenate, blue and green, have been described, which differ in composition and in certain properties from those described by Meyer.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Blue Chromium Selenate, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SeO}_4)_3, 17\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

A large excess of freshly prepared silver selenate was triturated with

a concentrated solution of chromium chloride. The mixture was kept aside for two days and then filtered. The blue filtrate was tested for silver and chlorine and any excess of either was removed by the cautious addition of chromium chloride or silver selenate. Any precipitate formed was removed by filtration. The blue solution was afterwards evaporated in a vacuum desiccator to dryness. The residue was digested with glacial acetic acid, filtered and kept in a desiccator over KOH till free from acetic acid. [Found: Cr, 12.46; Se, 28.39. $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SeO}_4)_3, 17\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cr, 12.40; Se, 28.27 per cent]. The substance forms a blue powder which loses 8 molecules of water at 105° , and 13.5 molecules at 165° .

Cryoscopic measurements.

Substance (g./100 c.c. water).	Dep. Δ .	Mol. wt. <i>m</i> .	Vant-Hoff's factor $i = \frac{m}{M}$	Degree of disso- ciation. $\alpha = \frac{i-1}{n-1}$.
1.590	0.146	196	2.719	0.43 approx.
0.795	0.088	162.6	3.278	0.57

$M = \text{mol. wt. calculated on anhydrous basis} = 533$

Molecular conductivity at 35° .

<i>v</i> (dilution in litres ...	128	256	512	1024	2048	4096
μ 411.39	476.93	542.21	621.21	718.85	814.56

The conductivity values correspond with those found for the violet chromium sulphate solution at the same temperature by Winston and Jones (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1911, **46**, 368).

<i>v</i> (dilution in litres) ...	128	512	1024	4096
μ 360.5	502	598	859

The *magnetic susceptibility* of the blue salt at 30° measured in a Curie's balance gave $\chi_m = 12.8 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\rho_{\text{wells}} = 18.0$.

The values are in good agreement with that for simple chromic ion.

The substance is very soluble in water. The solution of the blue salt becomes green on heating.

A freshly prepared blue solution treated with an excess of a solution of barium nitrate gives a white precipitate of barium selenate in the cold. The filtrate on boiling gives a further white precipitate of barium selenate. On treatment with dilute silver nitrate the solution of the blue salt gives a white precipitate after sometime. The solution reacts acid to litmus. This blue salt differs from the violet chromic selenate, described by Meyer, having the constitution $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SeO}_4)_3, 15$ or $16\text{H}_2\text{O}$, in which the whole of the selenate is completely and immediately precipitated by salts of barium. Moreover, the blue salt unlike Meyer's violet selenate gives no green precipitate of triselenato-chromic acid, $\text{H}_3[\text{Cr}(\text{SeO}_4)_3]$, when its boiling solution is treated with alcohol.

Green Chromium Selenate, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SeO}_4)_3, 13\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The blue solution of $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SeO}_4)_3, 17\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The green residue obtained was digested with glacial acetic acid and dried over solid KOH in a desiccator till free from acetic acid. [Found : Cr, 13.43; Se, 30.60. $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SeO}_4)_3, 13\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cr, 13.56; Se, 30.94 per cent]. The substance forms a beautiful green powder which loses 3.5 molecules of water at 105° and 6 molecules at 165° .

Cryoscopic measurements.

Substance (g./100 c.c. water).	Dep. Δ .	Mol. wt. <i>m</i> .	Vant Hoff's factor	Degree of disso- ciation.
			$f = \frac{m}{M}$	$\alpha = \frac{f-1}{n-1}$
1.5015	0.185	146.2	3.645	0.661
0.7505	0.106	127.6	4.186	0.796

(M. = Mol. wt. calculated on anhydrous basis = 533).

Molecular conductivity at 35° .

<i>v.</i> (dilution in litres)...	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	4096	
μ	422.21	481.02	546.56	611.84	691.2	759.8	847.87

The magnetic susceptibility of the green salt at 30° measured in a Curie's balance gave $\chi_m = 12.46 \times 10^{-6}$ and $p_{\text{weiss}} = 17.0$ approx.

The green salt is soluble in water with great difficulty to a green solution which reacts acid to litmus. The green solution on treatment with excess of barium nitrate gives a white precipitate of a barium selenate in the cold. The filtrate on boiling gives a further quantity of barium selenate. Silver nitrate solution gives a small quantity of silver selenate. The blue salt is easily convertible into the green variety with rise of temperature.

From a consideration of their properties it seems that there is a little difference in the behaviour of the two salts. The blue salt possibly contains less of selenate radical, co-ordinately bound, than the green variety. The green selenate described in this paper possibly corresponds with that described by Meyer differing only in the amount of hydration. The blue salt may be regarded as the intermediate product between Meyers' violet and green selenates as represented below :

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